

The Role of Yemeni Translators in Promotion Humanitarian Action in Yemen During the Civil War

دور المترجمين اليمنيين في تعزيز العمل الإنساني في اليمن أثناء الحرب الأهلية

Ahmed Mohammed Moneus
University of Sana'a, Yemen
Department of Translation
Moneus55@gmail.com

ISSN :2716-9359

EISSN :2773-3505

Received 04/04/2022

Accepted 27/06/2022

Published 01/07/2022

Abstract

Seven years have passed since the forgotten war in Yemen, as Western media called it. During these years, the Yemeni translator played a prominent role in promoting humanitarian work by accompanying international aid and medical staff their interventions and responses in an internally displaced person (IDP) camps, field hospitals, shelters, and food and drug distribution centres. This study aimed to examine the roles played by the Yemeni translators in promoting human actions and meet community needs. An interview was conducted with 10 Yemeni translators working in the field of relief and humanitarian actions in Yemen. The United Nations has classified Yemen as one of the worst humanitarian disasters in the world. Therefore, to meet the needs of society and the huge number of internally displaced people because of the ongoing conflict. Several international organizations provided urgent assistance to affected families and IDP camps, which required bilingual translators and assistants to provide field support, monitor the needs of indigenous people. The study found that Yemeni translators have played a key role in promoting humanitarian work, despite the difficulties and risks facing their works in the field. Therefore, this study recommended training the local translators by provide an adequate and up to date training for local translators who are working in the field of translation to reach effective and professional results.

Keywords: Aid, Conflict, Human action, Relief, Translation, War.

الملخص

سبع سنوات مضت على الحرب المنسية في اليمن، كما أطلق عليها الإعلام الغربي. خلال هذه السنوات، لعب المترجم اليمني دورًا بارزًا في تعزيز العمل الإنساني من خلال مرافقة المنظمات الدولية والطواقم الطبية أثناء تدخلاتهم واستجاباتهم في مخيمات النازحين والمستشفيات الميدانية والملاجئ ومراكز توزيع الغذاء والدواء. تهدف هذه الدراسة لتشخيص الأدوار التي يلعبها المترجمون اليمنيون في تعزيز الأعمال الإنسانية وتلبية احتياجات المجتمع. ولذلك أجريت مقابلة مع 10 مترجمين يمينيين يعملون في مجال الإغاثة والعمل الإنساني في اليمن. فلقد صنفت الأمم المتحدة اليمن كواحدة من أسوأ الكوارث الإنسانية في العالم. ولذلك، لتلبية احتياجات المجتمع والعدد الهائل من النازحين داخليا بسبب الصراع المستمر. قدمت العديد من المنظمات الدولية مساعدة عاجلة للأسر المتضررة ومخيمات النازحين داخليًا، الأمر الذي يتطلب وجود مترجمين ومساعدين ثنائيي اللغة لتقديم الدعم الميداني ورصد احتياجات السكان الأصليين ونقلها إلى عمال الإغاثة الأجانب. وتوصلت الدراسة أن المترجمين اليمنيين لعبوا دورًا رئيسيًا في تعزيز العمل الإنساني، على الرغم من الصعوبات والمخاطر التي تواجه أعمالهم في هذا المجال. ولذلك أوصت الدراسة بتدريب الكادر المحلي من خلال توفير تدريب ملائم وحديث للمترجمين الذين يعملون في مجال الترجمة للوصول إلى نتائج فعالة ومهنية.

الكلمات الدالة: الإغاثة، الترجمة، الحرب، الصراع، العمل الإنساني، المساعدات.

1. Introduction

Yemen faces a series of inter-related conflicts, in the past seven years, Yemen has been devastated by the civil war, the United Nations (UN) described crisis in Yemen as one of the worst crisis in the world. With so deteriorate economy and destroyed internal infrastructure. Yemen is currently experiencing the world's worst humanitarian crisis, destroying the country's humanitarian and economic infrastructure. The war in Yemen is changed the poor state into an unsustainable state that will be almost beyond irreparable. Yemen has been going through a historical turning point that has had an impact on the country's topography and future. Not far away, translation profession and translators affected as well. Tens of thousands of people have been killed and millions have gone hungry in the six-year conflict, leading to the world's worst humanitarian crisis. During seven - year conflict, dozens of thousands of people have been killed and millions are starving. The UN and the international community are demanding urgent action to save the human situation. Several International organizations have responded and implemented multiple rapid emergency response programs. With relief efforts to response a rapid-onset natural and to meet community needs. Yemen has seen a considerable increase in the number of international and local organizations working on humanitarian and relief issues, as well as political and social issues, in recent years, from 2011 to the present. International aid organizations are forced to hire bilingual speakers, language assistants and

translators to facilitate humanitarian operations on the ground. As a result, the reality on the ground necessitates an immediate response to a massive demand for humanitarian relief and life-saving measures. In response to an increase in the number of human workers and language speakers needed by international organizations to address community needs and facilitate humanitarian operations. In the realm of human activities, translators play a critical role in assisting humanitarian organizations during times of crises. Translators and language specialists collaborate with international organizations to help humanitarian and relief efforts. As a result, the role of Yemeni translators in the human crisis in Yemen is discussed in this paper.

2. Methodology

The methodology of the study relies on the qualitative research method, the interview was identified to determine the role of translators in supporting humanitarian organizations in Yemen. This study critically examined the roles of translators within war using a qualitative approach. It is employed to provide a more in depth understanding of the challenges faced by translators in conflict zone. So, the researcher found it the best way in collecting data. The qualitative approach was increasingly employed over the past few years in the social and human sciences, notably by translation scholars and researchers, it gains more interesting in social research. The interview was designed based on meeting with professional translation experts, they have proposed invite interviewees to open discussion. The interview instrument included seven questions that designed to derive from United Nations model that named competency-based interview (CBI), this modal allowing participants to talk about their situations based on previous experiences in interpreting the work.

3. Study Sample

Using video conference technology, ten professional translators accompanying relief and humanitarian operations were interviewed online, and their interviews were recorded and transcribed. The respondents in the sample requested that their names and workplaces remain anonymous. As a result, neither the workstation nor the participants' identities were mentioned.

4. Literature Review

Interpreters in human actions have a great impact on translation movements. "Translators and translators have been shown to play an important role in supporting the activities of the Non-governmental Organizations (NGOs) involved in crisis communication scenarios" (Federici & Cadwell, 2018, p. 20). Since March 2011, Yemen was experienced existence of hundreds of international organizations which are working in

different governorates of Yemen. According to the United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA, 2021), for the number of Organizations' Monthly Presence (May 2021), stated that "In May 2021, 107 organizations implemented Humanitarian Response Plan activities in 332 out of 333 districts in various ten sectors; food security, health, protection, nutrition, Water, Sanitation and Hygiene (WASH), Shelter, Rapid Response Mechanism (RRM), Camp Coordination and Camp Management (CCCM), Regional Multicultural Magnet School RMMS and Education. Therefore, unexpected increase in such NOGs required more communication with host communities", Bulut & Kurultay, (2001, p. 252) stated that "community interpreting contexts are frequently initiated by non-governmental organizations". Therefore, the work of a translator during periods of conflict could be divided into three categories:

1. Assisting in humanitarian relief operations by facilitating communication between supporting agencies and host communities.
2. Coordinating with governmental and non-governmental agencies and other relevant authorities in the field.
3. Assisting in solving problems that organizations workers may face in the field.

4.1 The Role of Translators in Promoting Humanitarian Aid Workers

Translator as supporting point in mediating and communicating between parties. "Translators can help ease survivors' sense of vulnerability and enable the response team to assess the situation and provide appropriate services more efficiently" (Gómez-Amich, M. (2017), p. 19). Most of translators played the role(s) during conflicts or immediately after they are hired to assist human organizations in organizing and facilitating of international staff works. In Yemen, most of local interpreters are working side by side with foreign staff to providing relief and food assistance for displaced population. Translators who participate in the time of crisis as a respond to the rules of supply and demand. Translation market in somehow activated during crises and conflict. Where "disaster interpreting is at the same time a field highly suited to voluntary work by professional translators and translators" (Bulut & Kurultay, 2001, p. 252). According to Moneus & Tajaddeen (2021, p.218), "the work of the translator involves multiple and various tasks that include all operations on the ground, such as support, backup, coordination, communication, liaising, mediation, facilitation, clarification and serving". Translators in crisis and the time of war may involve in additional tasks such as supporting humanitarian relief actions in the field they work with NGOs as Many large international NGOs, such as Oxfam International, Amnesty International, Save the Children, the International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies, CARE, and Specialized Agencies of the United Nations to coordination with local

host communities to meet population needs of food, medicine, infrastructure and Medical care. In similar regards, as a result of extended conflict, the refugee 'crisis' could not be managed without the help of volunteers translators. They play a very significant role and are confronted with highly challenging tasks (Schider, 2017). In line with Al-Shehari (2019, p.28) "The translators and interpreters believe that their role is to help people in need and convey their suffering to the people outside Yemen. Interestingly, they see themselves as advocates, going beyond the traditional descriptions of translation and interpreting". Therefore, Yemeni translators have involved in supporting INOs during crisis in Yemen. The Yemeni situation is a crisis translation situation (O'Brien, 2016).

4.2 The Role of Translators to Facilitate Communication

Moneus & Tajaddeen (2021) stated that the world faced a lot of conflicts, the matter that required the existence of a linguistic medium for transferring and making information substantial during mediation, conflicts, or intermediate wars". Translators in conflict zones are promoting independent interpreting between communicating parties. Translators have played a critical role in the time of war in mediation and facilitating (Todorova, 2016). Among various roles, the key role of translators is to facilitate communication, situations of conflict mediation. In some context, the translator find himself forced to act as mediator to mitigate of tension and approach both parties to the bargaining table. Therefore, the translator finds himself/herself in multi-tasking work. During the ongoing negotiations between the parties, the translator often plays a pivotal role in bringing the points of view between the two parties closer, reducing tension, and helping push the two parties to continue the negotiation process. Therefore, the translator's role as a linguistic conveyer from one language to another may go beyond to engage in secondary roles to assist in mediation process and bridge the gaps. According to Moneus & Tajaddeen (2021, p. 230), "the role played by the translator is no less important than the role of negotiators and mediators in wars".

4.3 The Role of Translators to Deal with Stressful Situations

According to Gomez Amich, (2017), Translators could be expectable face more pain when working in traumatic situations, including symptoms of stress and coping strategies. So, translators who are willing to work in relief work need to understand what is involved. Most of interpreters in conflict working under threaten and may be exposed to kill, track or murder. Bulut & Kurultay (2001) indicated that "the role of the translator in such cases is a matter of life and death" (p. 254). In such cases, the interpreters may have to face a lot of challenges in coordination and communication. Moneus & Tajaddeen (2021, p. 216) pointed that "interpreting in conflict zones are not

an easy task". The translator can also greatly contribute to easing conflicts, calming the burning atmosphere, and finding middle solutions by simplifying the meaning and calming angry souls. For example, one of the translators working with humanitarian organizations mentioned that in one of meetings between the two parties, the situation almost reached the point of a quarrel and almost got out of hand between delegates of international organizations and local delegates. Therefore, the translator was forced to intervene to calm everyone and seek to resolve the dispute in a diplomatic manner using his skills in negotiation and conflict resolution.

5. Study Question

What is the role of humanitarian translators in promoting humanitarian action in Yemen during the civil war?

6. Study Hypothesis

The null hypothesis in this study is that; *There is no professional need for humanitarian translators in promoting humanitarian operations.*

7. Data Collection

The researcher conducted an online interview with ten professional translators in Yemen who work for foreign organizations. To respond to the study's question "What is the role of the conflict zone translators in achieving professionalism and promoting humanitarian operations?" A competency-based interview was created by the researcher. UN uses these types of interviews to assess candidates' prior experience as translators, before sending the interview questions to validators, the researcher used this model and then sent them to three senior translation experts who reviewed and suggested changes before sending them to validators. (10) senior professional translators volunteered to participate in an online interview that consisted of seven open-ended questions to which they were invited to respond freely depending on their experience. The following are the interview questions:

1. How do you achieve professionalism in the difficult situation of interpretation you are facing?
2. What is the role of translators in promoting humanitarian operations?

For each one, the interview lasted 40 minutes. Their responses were recorded and written down by the researcher. All of their identities and organizations are kept strictly confidential at their request and approval. The interview phases of preparation and contact with translators took a long time, more than three months, and the researcher waited for their approval and leisure time to conduct the interview. After waiting and following for such a long time, the researcher finally got his wish and conducted the interview.

First, the researcher conducted extensive research to identify appropriate research questions and the best technique for gathering precise and accurate data from translators. After weeks of searching for information, the researcher discovered that the United Nations designed an international model for evaluating and testing translators based on their competencies and experiences.

Many interviews are founded on the idea that past success is the best predictor of future performance. In other words, your history tells a story about you: your talents, skills, abilities, knowledge, and actual experience in dealing with a variety of situations." As a result, the researcher adopted this model and created their own questions that met the research's objectives, then sent the questions to three senior translation professors for review and suggestions, after which the researcher had a dissection with the main advisor to ensure consistency and accuracy.

Second, the researcher distributes the final manuscript to 30 professors of translation, the majority of whom teach and practice translation at international universities all around the world. The referees modified certain questions grammatically and linguistically and included two new questions concentrating on the role of translators. As a result, the researcher requested the final approved document, which included the seven questions described earlier.

The steps that were taken to form the study instrument, as well as to assess the validity and reliability, are explained below:

1. In March 2020, conduct online meetings with senior translation academics using the Zoom technology.
2. Holding online meetings with competent translators in order to develop solid tools
3. Creating the initial draft of the instrument based on the results of the interviews
4. Meet with your principal advisor to discuss the first draft.
5. Creating a pre-final draft based on the comments of the advisor
6. After the adviser has accepted the pre-final draft, send it to the referees.
7. 30 international and national translation professors have requested to participate in examining and validating this instrument.
8. Conducting an online interview with the actual sample
9. Audio and video recording, transcription, coding, theme categorization, and discussion.

8. Data Analysis

The interview data was analyzed using Thematic Content Analysis (TCA). The most successful method for assessing interview information, according to the study, is thematic content analysis. The researchers then performed an online interview with humanitarian interpreters who work with international organizations in crisis zones. They were questioned and asked to answer questions based on their previous experience in working with humanitarian organizations. During the interview, two questions were asked, each focusing on a different component of the translator's work. All of the respondents responded to all of the questions, and the responses differed depending on the respondents' viewpoints. As a result, the interconnected responses were categorized and divided into various themes based on the respondents' shared notions, then sorted and arranged as seen in the discussion below.

8.1 Descriptive Coding

The interview data was classified into interrelated patterns and themes, with each patterns given its own color. The corelated themes were sorted upon related thoughts, while the unrelated ones were removed. Based on the data collected from the participants, the table below illustrates the sorting and coding of patterns for each question.

8.1.1 Analysis of Interview Questions

The analysis of the first question of the interview which is (Q1: *How do you achieve professionalism in the difficult situation of interpretation you are facing?*) is shown in Table (1).

Table 1.

The analysis of the first question of the interview

Patterns	<i>Black</i>	<i>Blue</i>	<i>Green</i>	<i>Orange</i>	<i>Red</i>	<i>Grey</i>
Participants	<i>Supporter</i>	<i>Professional</i>	<i>Communicator</i>	<i>Facilitator</i>	<i>Mediator</i>	<i>Moderator</i>
Participant 1	<i>Professionalism, in my point of view, can be acquired through confidence, competence, and knowledge. But, as interpreters, we may add "transparency", this character is very important in our career, as it safeguards the impartiality that we should always keep.</i>					
Participant 2	<i>This is based on the long experience one should be always trying hard to stay professional in his work and this could be achieved by early preparation for each subject matter you are translating</i>					
Participant 3	<i>I think there is several techniques that interpreter should sustain to keep professionalism during the working under pressure one of them the interpreter should always to make sure he is not part of conversation and he does not take any personal attitude or things against what they said.</i>					

Participant 4	<i>I think by taking more learn lessons from previous experience and keep you ready for any sudden task and be accurate and precise in conveying the meaning and work hard accordingly.</i>
Participant 5	<i>I think that I did not reach the level professionals so far, I feel sometimes that Arabic language that not help me that much to interpret everything clearly or as what you want, for example if the meeting is going to take more than one hour, I feel that the first hours woow there is no problem no falls and I feel little bit tired in the second hour may be, because may be that referred to lack of sleep or I have a daughter or I have more tasks to do. Sometimes when I finish the meetings, I just feel that I achieve 20% professional also I am working on my English, sometimes one said Arabic word that I do not know what does it mean, due to If I could understand what it does mean I could interpret, we face in such situation some unknown words that I could not interpret I think interpretation like I build up professionalism is a huge thing that we are seeking to achieve. I have situation in one of donors meeting I am ask to interpret after my maternal leave it is a long leave around month and as you know the topics of meeting already known to them, I feel that most of things that have been discussed I don't understand it, the issue that they talk about something they knows and I am like duff I don't figure out the speech, one of meeting member feel that I am lost he said do you understand the topic we talk about, I told him no, another meeting related the mental health I did so good in this meeting my colleague surprise that I am doing well and from that day I am accustomed to interpret I do around 25 meetings I feel I am going to be better day by day and I feel that I understand the speech and master the dialogue, also I witnessed public speaking I know that I have not long memory but I try to reach out that I will practice till I master this skills, also the note taking cause me problem I could not interpret with nots I prefer to concentrate on the speech instead of writing notes.</i>
Participant 6	<i>By getting very well prepared by develop your skills before you are doing interpretation you should familiar by human and context information and terms especially in your field. The translation is continued process so you could continue read and learn to achieve professionalism. Moreover, You have to be aware of ethics naturally, accuracy, culture awareness, proper terminology, all effects could be taken in your mind and reflected in reality, avoid biasness, etc.</i>
Participant 7	<i>To be translator should be professional in your work keeping accurate and clear meaning with honest in deliver the interpretation is the core of professionalism.</i>
Participant 8	<i>I don't think beyond the text and focus on conveying full meanings. Preparing before conducting any such task is the best way to reach professionalism as my work in the field of translation. I am accustomed to working with multi sectors and immense in different</i>

	projects. I implemented various minor and huge projects with my team. I am proud of my work as an interpreter, and I found that is the actual life I could not imagine myself without translation. It is my real world. are doing interpretation you should be familiar with human and context information and terms, especially in your field. The translation is a continuous process so you can continue to read and learn to achieve professionalism
Participant 9	<i>It is our duty to stick with professionalism in all our tasks when I interpret, I try my best to follow this value and deliver the speech as it is.</i>
Participant 10	<i>Professionalism means quality, which allows someone to perform his or her role to the best of his/her ability. However, maintaining professionalism in a difficult situation or under stress is unfortunately something most professionals encounter during their career. But in our business, being able to calm down and render the same message in the target language and remain calm in stressful situations means you have successfully maintained professionalism.</i>

The analysis of the second question of the interview which is (Q2: *What is the role of translators in promoting humanitarian operations?*) is shown in Table (2).

Table 2.

The analysis of the second question of the interview

Patterns	<i>Black</i>	<i>Blue</i>	<i>Green</i>	<i>Orange</i>	<i>Red</i>	<i>Grey</i>
Participants	<i>Supporter</i>	<i>Professional</i>	<i>Communicator</i>	<i>Facilitator</i>	<i>Mediator</i>	<i>Moderator</i>
Participant 1	<i>The interpreters, undoubtedly, play a vital role in promoting humanitarian operations; they work with NGOs and Humanitarian Rights Organizations to safeguard human rights and defend freedoms; they work with Humanitarian Aid Organizations to alleviate hunger and mitigate poverty; they work with Peacekeeping Operations to mediate warring parties and stop conflicts and resulting tragedies. In a nutshell, wherever there is a humanitarian work, there must be an interpreter. Interpreters have essential roles in supporting humanitarian aids and projects through clarifying and explaining community needs and what is going on the ground.</i>					
Participant 2	<i>The role of interpreters is always to send an optimistic message about humanitarian operations to make people trust this operation and showing it's positive impact in helping poor people in the difficult times.</i>					
Participant 3	<i>I think the interpreter play the critical role in promoting humanitarian activity most important through building understanding doners and international actors and local community beneficiaries.</i>					

Participant 4	<i>I try to apply humanitarian principle as much as possible because we are carrying out one of the noble message. To support the affected populations and communities, humanitarian workers need to communicate with different stakeholders and carry out negotiations by supporting the interpreters and translators. The role of the interpreter is to understand the dynamics of interpretation in humanitarian contexts.</i>
Participant 5	<i>Frankly speaking, I have problem could not remember the conditions in the conflicts that's a war in I will try to remember one because it is difficult to remember the conflict that not related to interpretation but for translation tasks, as you know in our translation field regarding the humanitarian operations there are foreigners who are going to go the field assisted a need and find out what are the need exactly, so they could not understand the humanitarian needs without interpretation, the interpreters like the ears of foreigners in the field, they could not move without them, they are going to hear from citizens and I am going to interpret their needs, clarifies their issues, reflect the suffering the people, we know that Yemen going through crisis and we have the war and conflict and we have lot of things need to treatment. A lot of people lost their foods, all of these if we want what they need and how they deliver their suffering to international staff, interpreting is existed to assist and deliver their messages. The role of interpreters not only deliver the speech between two parts, but they provide a great help and service to vulnerable communities during writing their needs and advise relevant authorities.</i>
Participant 6	<i>Very critical that must vary that, the interpreter should be aware communicative role, beware of context, the interpreter should be part of negation process because very critical and important for humanitarian processes I recommend any interpreter should involve in humanitarian interpretations to read a lot about humanitarian negotiations rules, that will grant him impression about how he should behave during supporting persons who work in the field to assist and provide aids to citizens.</i>
Participant 7	<i>They have a major role in conveying the actual realities, response and feedback as accurate and professional as possible. Efficient interpreter would contribute to preventing any insignificant dispute or misunderstanding and would raise the operations on a higher profile with the main stakeholders including mass media and donors.</i>
Participant 8	<i>Interpreters are tools to deliver messages of speakers who are the main players in promoting humanitarian operations .</i>
Participant 9	<i>Interpreters are essential roles in supporting humanitarian aids and projects through clarify and explain community needs and what are going on the ground. Translation as a language of mediation naturally exists since language was originated.</i>
Participant 10	<i>To support the affected populations, humanitarian professionals need to communicate with different stakeholders and carry out negotiations</i>

	<i>with the support of interpreters. Ideally, interpreters provide interpretations for the humanitarian professionals who do not speak the local language. So, it lies on the interpreters to build trust with the community and stakeholders and not only render sheer words. So it is the role of the interpreter to understand the dynamics of interpretation in humanitarian contexts and bridge the language barrier during a humanitarian negotiation and work.</i>
--	---

8.1.2 Generating Themes

The researcher classified the themes according to their correlations with the main concept of the interview after sorting and coding the patterns, six themes were generated upon participant' point of views, while excluding the unrelated themes as in Table (3):

Table 3.

Generating Themes and Code Description

Themes	Code Description
<i>Translator as Supporter</i>	<i>Participants reinforce interpreters work in two ways: (a) interpreters is a culture bridge and focal point between local citizens and international workers (b) interpreters bridge the gap between two parts, persons, parties and fostering the human actions</i>
<i>Translator as professional</i>	<i>Participants focused on interpreter work</i>
<i>Translator as Mediator</i>	<i>Participants confirm on role of interpreter as mediator</i>
<i>Translator as Communicator</i>	<i>Participants emphasized that interpreters play different roles such as conveying message and carrying culture aspects</i>
<i>Translator as Facilitator</i>	<i>Participants share their ideas about role of interpreters in dealing with different situations</i>
<i>Translator as moderator</i>	<i>Participants agreed that interpreter' role include contributing to elevating conflict</i>

9. Discussion and Interpretation

The data was analyzed using an inductive approach. This meant carefully reviewing each response and identifying key themes and recurring problems in the person's story based on interview questions that we had pre-determined. The researcher used typical qualitative procedures in the data analysis below, quoting critical interview responses, coding and classifying the data in associated themes based on the sample's responses, and serving the study work's aim. All of their identities were kept completely secret. Nonetheless,

all participants gave their consent for the researcher to utilize their information in this study.

To answer the question of the study "What is the role of the Yemeni translators in achieving professionalism and promoting humanitarian operations?" The Thematic Content Analysis (TCA) was used. The researcher found that thematic content analysis was the best way to analyze interview data. Thereupon, the researcher conducted an online interview with humanitarian translators. They were questioned on interpretation in crisis settings. The data was coded and categorized into themes as follows.

9.1 Translator as Humanitarian Aid Supporter

Translators are commonly hired due they spoke two or more languages besides the language of international relief organizations. The key role of translators during a humanitarian crisis is supporting and promoting international aid workers in the field. Most of the respondents confirmed that translators and translators are involved primarily in providing urgent services in multi sectors that meet community needs. According to Gomez Amich (2017) Translators could assist relieve survivors' feelings of vulnerability and enable the response team to evaluate the situation and furnish convenient services more competently. Participants agreed that translators' work should reinforce human actions, the translators are the bridge of understandings the gap between parties. One respondent stated:

"Translators and translators are the only bridge between two persons who speak different languages" (personal communication, November 21, 2021).

Another one stated:

"Translators have essential roles in supporting humanitarian aids and projects through clarifying and explaining community needs and what is going on the ground" (personal communication, November 21, 2021).

One respondent stated:

"To support the affected populations and communities, humanitarian workers need to communicate with different stakeholders and carry out negotiations by supporting the translators and translators" (personal communication, November 21, 2021).

Furthermore, the translators are supporting the affected communities and promoting humanitarian works. They played essential roles in implementing human aid projects. According to (Shepherd-Barron, 2010), Languages can

act as a crucial barrier for effective communication in the delivery of aid, as has been pointed out about recent evaluations of international humanitarian assistance.

Therefore, one of the respondents reported that:

"Ideally, translators provide interpretations for the humanitarian professionals who do not speak the local language. So, it lies on the translators to build trust with the community and stakeholders" (personal communication, November 21, 2021).

Some respondents linked supporting human actions and negotiation process; they confirm that translators bridge the language barrier during their interpretation. They stated that providing interpretations for the humanitarian professionals and providing interpretations for the humanitarian professionals are the pushing motives for facilitating human operations on the ground.

One of the respondents stated:

"The role of the translator to understand the dynamics of interpretation in humanitarian contexts. and bridge the language barrier during a humanitarian negotiation and work" (personal communication, November20, 2021).

Another one said:

"The role of translators not only deliver the speech between two parts, but they provide a great help and service to vulnerable communities during writing their needs and advise relevant authorities" (personal communication, November 20, 2021).

Consequently, Delgado Luchner & Kherbiche (2019) indicated that many translators work in affected areas, not as military translators, but as national staff hired to work for humanitarian organizations. To that end, as various ethic issues that translators in conflict areas encountered consequence from the implied armed fight itself, other translators may face the same, particularly translators who are working with humanitarian organizations to provide support to vulnerable communities by conflict. The ICRC and the UNHCR translator represent two archetypes of humanitarian translators (Delgado Luchner & Kherbiche, 2018). In addition, humanitarian translators should be involved in facilitating the access of international aid to beneficiaries. Also, they mentioned that numerous translators work in conflict zones, not as military translators, but as civilians working for humanitarian organizations.

9.2 Translator as professional (Professionalism)

Some respondents stated that achieving professionalism can be through maintaining some cognitive competencies. Adequate Knowledge, reading, and paying much attention to terminology can help achieve professionalism. In addition, being aware of details and having self-confidence are also factors leading to professionalism.

One respondent says:

"Professionalism, in my point of view, can be acquired through confidence, competence, and knowledge. But, as translators, we may add "transparency", this character is very important in our career, as it safeguards the impartiality that we should always keep" (personal communication, November 21, 2021).

Another one added:

"Professionalism means quality, which allows someone to perform his or her role to the best of his/her ability. However, maintaining professionalism in a difficult situation or under stress is, unfortunately, something most professionals encounter during their career" (personal communication, November 21, 2021).

Another one stated:

"We must stick with professionalism in all our tasks when I interpret, I try my best to follow this value and deliver the speech as it is" (personal communication, November 21, 2021).

Some respondents refer the role of translator to his/her experience in interpreting. Others think that experience is the main factor for achieving professionalism. The longer experience a translator has, the closer he gets to achieving professionalism.

One respondent stated:

"Think by taking more learn lessons from previous experience and keep you ready for any sudden task and be accurate and precise in conveying the meaning and work hard accordingly" (personal communication, November 21, 2020).

Another one stated:

"This is based on the long experience one should be always trying hard to stay professional in his work and this could be achieved by early preparation for each subject matter you are translating" (personal communication, November 21, 2021).

Another one stated:

"I have been working as a translator and translator for 15 years and have acquired a rich experience in both fields. Throughout this career, I have encountered fear, stress and dealt with different challenges" (personal communication, November 21, 2021).

Another one added:

"I have deep experience that enables me to work with an international organization that I work and enjoy the interpretation with foreigners I feel that I present a great service for those who do not speak our tongue" (personal communication, November 21, 2020).

Furthermore, Competency and experience could share common ground more experience you have more competencies will have. One of the respondents narrated his story by interpreting:

"I am working as a translator I could describe the translator as the driver of the vehicle to drive the vehicle you need to check all parts oil, water, heat, and others. So interpretation needs a lot of focus I mean fluency in English, level of consumption, the context having a lot of vocabulary, aware of culture, traditions, summarize what already cited, to be a good translator is a matter of time, tell me how many you interpret, I tell you how you are, I joined many workshops, similar meetings and conversations as translator, I had started with the company when I was senior level at University as invitation of the company so the first driving I joined interpretation inspired me a lot to read more to listen more, to practice more, to have many training sessions, to meet more experts particularly, after 2013 I joined many jobs such as teaching, translating and later on programming in an organization that referred to projects. ON of my duties, I have to interpret as program coordinator needs" (personal communication, November 21, 2020).

Others think that preparation can help achieve professionalism. In addition, preparing oneself to know the contexts and cultural differences helps him be more professional. Yet, most of the respondents stressed the importance of previous preparation.

One of the respondents stated:

"By getting very well prepared by developing your skills before you are doing interpretation you should be familiar with human and context information and terms especially in your field. The

translation is a continued process so you could continue to read and learn to achieve professionalism" (personal communication, November 21, 2020).

Another respondent added:

"Preparing before conducting any such task is the best way to reach professionalism as my work in the field of translation. I am accustomed to working with multi sectors and immense in different projects I implemented various minor and huge projects with my team I am proud of my work as a translator, and I found that is the actual life I did not imagine myself without translation it's my real world" (personal communication, November 21, 2020).

Some respondents are stated that professionalism could be related to impartiality, one of the respondents stated:

"I think there are several techniques that translator should sustain to keep professionalism during the working under pressure one of them the translator should always make sure he is not part of the conversation, and he does not take any personal attitude or things against what they said" (personal communication, November 21, 2021).

Another one added:

"As a professional translator, I always make it clear from the beginning that I am a Neutral person who does his job with high professionalism. Always say I am just a translator doing his job professionally. I have no interest in either party" (personal communication, November 21, 2021).

Accuracy is the backbone of the whole process of interpreting, translators should transfer the meaning correctly, and accuracy.

One of the respondents stress accuracy:

"The translator to reach out the professionalism in his work, he should keep accurate and clear meaning with honest in delivering the interpretation is the core of professionalism" (personal communication, November 21, 2021).

Another one added:

"I try during my work to be accurate in translating texts and delivering the speech because any minor mistakes may change the whole meaning, I work in the medical field I like to translate and

interpreted I feel medical terms dancing before my eyes" (personal communication, November 21, 2021).

Another narration explains the degree of accuracy and understanding beyond the meaning, one of the respondents stated:

"I think that I did not reach the level professionals so far, I feel sometimes that the Arabic language that not help me that much to interpret everything clearly or as what you want, for example, if the meeting is going to take more than one hour I feel that the first hours wow there is no problem no falls and I feel a little bit tired in the second hour maybe because maybe that referred to lack of sleep or I have a daughter or I have more tasks to do" (personal communication, November21, 2021).

In the long run, humanitarian translators are adherence to ensuring that their works will stand in supporting and empowering those who need it most. According to (Delgado Luchner & Kherbiche, 2019) the professionalization of translators thus depends on the capacity of other humanitarian actors to make adequate use of a linguistic mediator.

9.3 Translator as Communicator

The respondents reported that one of the roles that translators perform is the communicative role. Participants emphasized that translators play a communicative role in conveying messages and carrying cultural aspects. One of the respondents who have worked with relief organization stated that:

"In one session, actually a part of the session, I found myself moving from historical context about mummies and ways of mummification to another context of discussing natural resources, mineral wealth, fisheries and livestock, to another context of bee-breeding and the best types and resources of honey in the world. So, translators are very much eligible for multiculturalism and world citizenship" (personal communication, November 21, 2020).

Another one stated:

"During interpreting, I do think beyond the text and focus on conveying full meanings" (personal communication, November 21, 2021).

According to Businario (2012, p. 7) "Today, contacts between people with different linguistic and cultural backgrounds have increased significantly as communication takes place for various purposes, such as business, education, media, tourism, art, immigration, political conflicts".

One of the respondents said:

"I think that the real role of the translator is to communicate between the parties and convey the facts and meanings as stated by the other party" (personal communication, November 21, 2021).

Some respondents agreed on the role of the translator as a communicator:

"We prefer to concentrate on the speech instead of writing notes should interpret everything and could not change anything, we are communicators, we use order in our assignments sometimes we ask the speaker to repeat or to say exactly what he or she wants to say" (personal communication, November 21, 2021).

Therefore, the communication process is one of the primary and core mandate of the translator in transferring information between the parties as needed.

9.4 Translator as Mediator

Some respondents stated that translators also work as mediators to help people and negotiate between two feuding parties. They stated that changing the role of translators has still not acceptable, but the situation adjacent sometimes forced translators to act accordingly.

One respondent stated:

"I have had many exciting experiences I have been through several situations where I mediated and facilitated dialogue between parties from different works, I think I do it" (personal communication, November 21, 2021).

Another one stated:

"Translation as a language of mediation naturally exists since language was originated" (personal communication, November 21, 2021).

Respondents from those who have already worked with international organizations confirmed that one reason beyond the role of the translator as a mediator is that the nature of dialogue in a particular context pushes you to act as a mediator.

One professional translator stated:

"The translator should try his or her best to calm them down and attempts, if possible, to provide clarifications and work as a mediator that would help calm down the hostile situation when

matters come out the control" (personal communication, November 21, 2021).

Another respondent stated:

"I would try my best to calm things, stop the ragging conversations, bring them to the negotiations' table" (personal communication, November 21, 2021).

The experience reason may also be for improving skills and competencies in the profession of mediation as stated by this respondent:

"I have had many exciting experiences I have been through several situations where I meditated and facilitated dialogue between parties from different works, I think I do it" (personal communication, November 21, 2021).

This data comes to support Bassnett (2011) emphasis placed on examining the role of the translator as a bilingual translator and as a figure whose role is to mediate between cultures. Also, Bedeker & Feinauer (2009) described the translator as a cultural mediator who is responsible for successful cross-cultural communication. According to Delgado Luchner & Kherbiche (2019) the ICRC and the UNHCR also depend on the linguistic mediator for their implementation mandate and communicate with their beneficiaries.

9.5 Translator as Facilitator

According to Moneus & Tajaddeen (2021, p. 216), "Simultaneous interpretation is an active component of dialogue, negotiation, conversation, meetings, mediations, conferences, seminars, health groups, delegations, deliberations, and consultations.

"The key role of the translator is to facilitate the process of communication between the speaker and the receiver, taking into account the rules of the transmitted speech" (personal communication, November 21, 2021).

Respondents stated that if they do not understand what the speaker said, they would politely ask him to pause and say what he said again and slowly. This helps them be more focused and get what the speaker said.

One respondent said:

"I would gently ask him to speak slowly and so I deliver accurate interpretation and avoid confusion and unnecessary misunderstanding to the interpretation recipients. If that repeated, I would agree with him to give me the chance to interpret sentence by

sentence" (personal communication, November 21, 2021).

In that event, Bulut, & Kurultay (2001) the translators reported that they tried their best to facilitate the team's work and operations, and that they would facilitate directly with the locals for almost the same purpose. Proportionately, the role of facilitator essentially associated with humanitarian translator, so the key role of translators in humanitarian organizations is related deeply during facilitating access and communicate with local residents.

9.6 Translator as moderator

Participants share their ideas about the role of translators in dealing with different situations particularly when translators face offensive and aggressive situations, the participants agreed on softness and diplomatic way in behave, one of the respondents said:

"Of Course, I will ask him to clarify or rephrase the incomprehensible part of his speech, to get a clear message and convey it as clear as received" (personal communication, November 21, 2021).

Another stated:

"I will ask them to pause and repeat what he said or ask for more clarification politely and kindly that he did not feel that I am interrupted him" (personal communication, November 21, 2021).

Another one explained reaction in such context:

"Generally, speakers who have worked with translators often consider the translator and cooperate with them during interpretation so them. But if I don't understand what the speaker has said during interpretation, I will ask the speaker to repeat what he/she has said and ask him /her to allow time for interpretation" (personal communication, November 21, 2021).

In other regards, Businario (2012) stated that various kinds of interpreting are generally used according to the mode of delivery and setting (eg: consecutive, simultaneous, media, escort..), that supported by one of the respondents that reported:

"That happens during consecutive interpretation when delegation speaks a word that unfamiliar to me, so I impose to ask him to explain what exactly means by this or that word because the duty of translator to be accurate in translation so I will ask to understand" (personal communication, November 21, 2021).

Some respondent stated:

"Usually, we ask them to pause and slowly repeat what they have said. Politely ask them to rephrase what they mean. Or also ask them politely to clarify what they mean. You need to be confident enough to ask for clarification but also nicely and respectfully" (personal communication, November 21, 2021).

Another respondent referred this to the kind of interpretation:

"I think it depends on interpretation simultaneous or consecutive also we have a note-taker, of course, there are techniques that filling the gaps to overcome the hesitated. However, I should ask him to repeat what he is saying specifically if the conference or the interpretation task is very important referring to numbers, critical issues because the translator could work as a mediator, so I can ask him to stop and ask him for more clarifying, what does he mean, in this case, if having written in note-taking, I will go back to information that I wrote" (personal communication, November 21, 2021).

It is noted that, the note taker, translator and moderator are three characters in one, the translator during interpretation is forced to take notes and act as moderator particularly in consecutive interpreting.

10. Findings

Based on the foregoing discussion, the results of the interview, the data of the participants. This study analyzed the roles of translators in achieving professionalism and promoting humanitarian operations, the following findings are obtained: translators play a major role in supporting relief operations and humanitarian responses, this finding is in line with (Moneus & Tajaddeen, 2021) who stated that the main role of translators during the crisis to support the humanitarian work and provide services that meet community needs. The roles of the translator vary depending on the nature of the work. The translator performs the role of communicating, coordinating, mediating, moderating, managing sessions, and facilitating communication between the parties. The pivotal role of translators of humanitarian organizations is to support relief operations on the ground. Professionalism is also important as a value in a translator's work and is achieved by seeking credibility, integrity, experience, and good preparation. This study disagrees with Businario (2012) that finds humanitarian organizations, although being aware of the importance of effective communication with local residents, they do not care about hiring professional interpreters who have unique skills in interpretations.

It is worth noting that, the translator's multiple and interrelated roles are not a product of the moment, but rather the product of an integrated system of works that the translator is entrusted with. This data was supported by Al-Shehari (2019, p. 28) "The translators and interpreters believe that their role is to help people in need and convey their suffering to the people outside Yemen. Interestingly, they see themselves as advocates, going beyond the traditional descriptions of translation and interpreting". Therefore, the roles of the translator during crises are many and varied, in addition to his basic work in translation, it may include other areas such as support, advocacy, logistical support, assistance, promotion, facilitation, coordination, communication, networking, and when the need arises to performs other related duties as required. Although there are many roles for translators that accompany with relief aid organizations but the researcher selected the most prominent roles based on data gathered from respondents.

11. Conclusions

Although there are many roles for translators that accompany with relief aid organizations, but the researcher selected the most prominent roles based on data gathered from respondents. Upon the data collected and discussion above, it is noted that translators accompany by humanitarian organizations are considered professional translators, they do not work in the humanitarian field, but they acquire experience during their work and find their selves involve in many roles. The results of the interview revealed that in the times of crisis, translators play a critical role in advancing humanitarian efforts. These roles include facilitation, coordination, communication, mediating, supporting, moderating, and achieving professionalism with other related roles. The study data clearly demonstrated the importance of existing translators accompanying human aid operations, leading to the rejection of null hypotheses such as "there is no professional need for humanitarian translators in promoting humanitarian operations".

This study recommended the following:

1. Yemen humanitarian translators needs awareness trainings in human relief knowledge to act their roles accordingly.
2. Held interpreting course in humanitarian terms used in international organizations.
3. Training courses for local translators and translators about human relief operations.
4. The humanitarian organizations must be aware of the importance of selecting professional translators due to the essential roles that translators play in communication and coordination.

References

- Al-Shehari, K. (2019). Crisis translation in Yemen: Needs and challenges of volunteer translators and translators. In *Translation in Cascading Crises* (pp. 25-45). Routledge.
- Businario, R. (2012). Relief operations across language barriers: the translator factor. *Unpublished MSc thesis, University College Dublin*.
- Bassnett, S. (2011). The translator as a cross-cultural mediator. *Oxford Handbooks Online*.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780199239306.013.0008>
- Bulut, A., & Kurultay, T. (2001). Translators-in-Aid at disasters. *The Translator*, 7(2), 249-263. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13556509.2001.10799104>
- Delgado Luchner, C., & Kherbiche, L. (2019). Ethics training for humanitarian translators working in conflict and post-conflict settings. *Journal of War & Culture Studies*, 12(3), 251-267.
- Federici, F. M., & Cadwell, P. (2018). Training citizen translators. *Translation and Interpreting in Non-Governmental Organisations*, 7(1), 20-43. <https://doi.org/10.1075/ts.00002.fed>
- Gomez Amich, M. (2017). Descriptive Study on the Self-Perception of Interpreters in Conflict Zones: A Case Study in Afghanistan (Doctoral dissertation, University of Granada). Retrieved from https://www.academia.edu/37798882/G%C3%B3mez-Amich_M_2017_Descriptive_Study_on_the_Self-Perception_of_Interpreter_in_Conflict_Zones_A_Case_Study_in_Afghanistan.
- Luchner, C. D., & Kherbiche, L. (2018). Without fear or favour?: The positionality of ICRC and UNHCR interpreters in the humanitarian field. *Target. International Journal of Translation Studies*, 30(3), 408-429.
- Moneus, A. M., & Tajaddeen, I. (2021). Translators in The Time of Crisis: Borders and Barriers. *ALANDALUS Journal for Humanities & Social Sciences*, 8(51), 215-233.
- O'Brien, S. (2016). Training translators for crisis communication: translators without borders as an example. In *Mediating Emergencies and Conflicts* (pp. 85-111). Palgrave Macmillan, London.
- OCHA. (2021). *Yemen: Organizations' Monthly Presence (May 2021) [EN/AR]*. Reliefweb. Retrieved from [Yemen: Organizations' Monthly Presence \(November 2021\) \[EN/AR\] - Yemen | ReliefWeb](https://reliefweb.int/yemen/organizations-monthly-presence-november-2021)

Schider, S. (2017). *Translators as agents in the refugee crisis* (Doctoral dissertation). Retrieved from [Interpreters as Agents in the Refugee Crisis - heiDOK \(uni-heidelberg.de\)](http://www.uni-heidelberg.de/interpreters-as-agents-in-the-refugee-crisis)

Shepherd-Barron, J. (2010). Language Skills. *UNICEF-APSSC*, [online] Available at: < [http://www.seameo.org/LanguageMDGConference2010/doc/Accessed September, 12, 2016](http://www.seameo.org/LanguageMDGConference2010/doc/Accessed%20September%2C%2012%2C%202016)

Todorova, M. (2016). Interpreting conflict mediation in Kosovo and Macedonia. *Linguistica Antverpiensia, New Series—Themes in Translation Studies*, 15, 227–240.